

Mixed Signal Detection and Symbol Rate Estimation based on Spectral Coherent Features

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Abstract—Signal detection and RF parameter estimation have received great interest in recent years due to the need for spectrum sensing in rapidly growing cognitive radio and cyber security research. In most conventional signal detection and RF parameter estimation work, the target signal is often assumed to be a single primary user signal without overlap in spectrum with other signals. However, in a spectrally congested environment or a spectrally contested environment which often occurs in cyber security applications, multiple signals are often mixed together with significant overlap in spectrum. In our previous work, we have demonstrated the feasibility of using a second order spectrum correlation function (SCF) cyclostationary feature to perform mixed signal detection, but the detection was confined to BPSK modulation. In this paper, we extend our work to QPSK modulation by using a robust algorithm to detect mixed signals and estimate their symbol rate via spectral coherence function (SOF) features. We also evaluate the detection and estimation performance of the proposed algorithm in various channel conditions and signal mixture scenarios. Simulation results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed scheme.

I. INTRODUCTION

Signal detection and RF parameter estimation have been growing for many decades [1]- [9]. However, in most existing work, the target signal is often assumed to be a single signal without overlap in spectrum with other signals. This assumption is becoming more and more invalid with the recent development of cognitive radio network since multiple secondary users might try to grasp the same spectrum hole and such signals also need to be detected and analyzed to avoid interference. In the spectrally contested environment one often faces in cyber security applications, multiple signals from friendly transmitters and hostile transmissions may also coexist and significantly overlap in the same frequency band. Hence, it is highly desired to develop an effective scheme to detect the existence of multiple users' signals, identify how many signals are mixed together, and estimate their RF parameters.

In our previous work, presented in last year's Milcom [10], we demonstrated the feasibility of using a second order spectrum correlation function (SCF) cyclostationary feature [11]- [15] to perform mixed signal detection. However, in this work, the detection was confined to BPSK modulation. Here, we extend our work to include QPSK modulation by using a robust algorithm to detect mixed signals and estimate their

symbol rate via spectral coherence function (SOF) features [11]- [15]. By employing SOF features, we are able to find a stable threshold in our mixed signal detection algorithm to determine how many mixed components are present. We have thoroughly evaluated the detection and symbol rate estimation performance under various channel conditions and signal mixture scenarios. Simulation results confirm the effectiveness and robustness of our algorithm.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the system model of the mixed signal detection. Section III briefly reviews the second-order cyclostationary feature and discusses the mixed signal detection algorithm based on SOF. In Section IV, we evaluate the signal detection and symbol rate estimation performance of the proposed algorithm and demonstrate the effectiveness and robustness of the algorithm in various channel conditions and signal mixture scenarios. Simulation results at different signal to noise ratio and channel conditions validate the advantage and reliability of the proposed method. The conclusion follows in Section V.

II. MIXED SIGNAL DETECTION

In a spectrally congested or spectrally contested environment, multiple signals may overlap significantly in frequency domain. Fig. 1 shows the spectrum of a mixed signal with two narrow-band signal components with very close carrier frequencies so that there is a 100% spectrum overlap (the spectrum overlap is defined as the overlapping spectrum divided by the minimum bandwidth of all signal components). It is obvious that we can no longer tell that there are two signal components by simple frequency analysis, and we cannot use a narrow-band filter to distinguish one signal from the other.

III. SOF BASED MIXED SIGNAL DETECTION AND SYMBOL RATE ESTIMATION

A. Second-order Cyclostationary Features and Spectral Coherence Function

It is well-known that many man-made signals, such as communication and radar signals are cyclostationary random processes. The first-order or second-order statistic characteristics (average value, correlation function, etc) of such man-made signals often show a periodicity. The periodic features of these signals are not reflected in the conventional power spectrum.

Fig. 1. Spectrum mixed signal with two different components (100% spectrum overlap)

By exploiting the correlation characteristics between different frequency bands, we can reveal these periodic features and perform signal detection, RF parameter estimation, and even modulation detection [3]- [9].

In our previous work [10], we have demonstrated the feasibility of detecting mixed signals with significant spectrum overlap using second order cyclostationary spectrum correlation function features. However, as shown in [10], the SCF based algorithm doesn't provide a fixed threshold value for detection and a heuristic algorithm needs to be performed to find an appropriate detection threshold.

Hence, we use SOF which is a normalized version of SCF to solve this problem. Assume $x(t)$ is a cyclostationary signal, its SOF defined in [11]- [16] as:

$$C_x^\alpha(f) = \frac{S_x^\alpha(f)}{\left[S_x^0\left(f + \frac{1}{2}\alpha\right)^* S_x^0\left(f - \frac{1}{2}\alpha\right) \right]^{1/2}}, \quad (1)$$

where α is the cyclic frequency, f is the spectrum frequency. $S_x^\alpha(f)$ is the SCF, which is the Fourier transformation of the cyclic autocorrelation function $R_x^\alpha(\tau)$

$$S_x^\alpha(f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} R_x^\alpha(\tau) e^{-j2\pi f\tau} d\tau. \quad (2)$$

It is shown that the SOF is upper-bounded by unity (shown in Eq.(3)) and can help to remove channel effect [12]:

$$|C_X^\alpha(f)| \leq 1. \quad (3)$$

Additionally, SOF has an invariance property [12], which means it will not be affected by linear time-invariant transformations. Hence, we can use SOF and find a universal threshold for our mixed signal detection purposes.

B. SCF and SOF of BPSK and QPSK signal

The spectral correlation function of BPSK and QPSK signals are given in [16].

1) *SCF and SOF of BPSK signal*: For a BPSK signal $x(t) = a(t) \cos(2\pi f_c t + \phi_0)$, in which $a(t) = \sum_{-\infty}^{\infty} a_n q(t - nT_0 - t_0)$ where a_n is bits information, f_c is carrier frequency, T_0 is symbol duration, t_0 is time delay, and ϕ_0 is phase offset, the SCF of BPSK signal [16] is

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{S}_x^\alpha(f) = \frac{1}{4T_0} \cdot \left\{ \left[Q\left(f + f_c + \frac{\alpha}{2}\right) Q^*\left(f + f_c - \frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \tilde{S}_a^\alpha(f + f_c) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + Q\left(f - f_c + \frac{\alpha}{2}\right) Q^*\left(f - f_c - \frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \tilde{S}_a^\alpha(f - f_c) \right] \cdot \exp[-j2\pi\alpha t_0] \right. \\ \left. + Q\left(f + \frac{\alpha}{2} + f_c\right) Q^*\left(f - \frac{\alpha}{2} - f_c\right) \tilde{S}_a^{\alpha+2f_c}(f) \right. \\ \left. \cdot \exp[-j(2\pi[\alpha + 2f_c]t_0 + 2\phi_0)] \right. \\ \left. + Q\left(f + \frac{\alpha}{2} - f_c\right) Q^*\left(f - \frac{\alpha}{2} + f_c\right) \tilde{S}_a^{\alpha-2f_c}(f) \right. \\ \left. \cdot \exp[-j(2\pi[\alpha - 2f_c]t_0 - 2\phi_0)] \right\}, \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

where $q(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & |t| \leq T_0/2 \\ 0, & |t| > T_0/2 \end{cases}$, and $Q(f) = \frac{\sin(\pi f T_0)}{\pi f}$.

For bits sequence a_n , we have

$$\tilde{S}_a^\alpha(f) = \begin{cases} \tilde{R}_a(0), & \alpha = k/T_0 \\ 0, & \alpha \neq k/T_0 \end{cases}, |k| = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

here we assume $\tilde{R}_a(0) = 1$, and k is an integer.

According to the spectral correlation function Eq.(4), if we focus on $f = f_c$ projection of the SCF, we can derive that

$$\hat{S}_x^\alpha(f_c)_{(BPSK)} = \frac{T_0}{2} \text{sinc}^2\left(\frac{k}{2}\right), \quad \alpha = \frac{k}{T_0}, |k| = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (5)$$

where $\text{sinc}(x) = \frac{\sin(\pi x)}{\pi x}$. According to Eq.(1), we know that $\hat{S}_x^\alpha(f_c)_{(BPSK)}$ shows a fixed feature when $f = f_c$ and $\alpha = k/T_0$. We can then obtain the SOF of BPSK signal as:

$$C_x^\alpha(f_c)_{(BPSK)} = 1, \quad \text{when } \alpha = k/T_0, |k| = 1, 3, 5, \dots \quad (6)$$

The SCF and SOF of a BPSK signal are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. In these figures, the carrier frequency is $f_c = 20000$ Hz, the null-to-null bandwidth of the signal $B = 5000$ Hz, hence the symbol rate $R_s = 2500$ Hz. The time delay t_0 and phase offset ϕ_0 are set to be 0. Here, we just focus on $f = f_c$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1.2R_s)$ projection.

2) *SCF and SOF of QPSK signal*: It is well known that any time-series signal $x(t)$ can be expressed in the quadrature-amplitude modulation (QAM) form $x(t) = c(t) \cos(2\pi f_c t + \phi_0) - s(t) \sin(2\pi f_c t + \phi_0)$. For QPSK modulation, we have $c(t) = \sum_{-\infty}^{\infty} c_n q(t - nT_0 - t_0)$, $s(t) = \sum_{-\infty}^{\infty} s_n q(t - nT_0 - t_0)$, and its SCF is represented in [16] as Eq.(7):

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{S}_x^\alpha(f) = \frac{1}{2T_0} \cdot \left[Q\left(f + \frac{\alpha}{2} + f_c\right) Q^*\left(f - \frac{\alpha}{2} + f_c\right) \tilde{S}_c^\alpha(f + f_c) \right. \\ \left. + Q\left(f + \frac{\alpha}{2} - f_c\right) Q^*\left(f - \frac{\alpha}{2} - f_c\right) \tilde{S}_c^\alpha(f - f_c) \right] \cdot \exp(-j2\pi\alpha t_0), \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

in which

$$\tilde{S}_i^\alpha(f) = \begin{cases} \tilde{R}_i(0), & \alpha = k/T_0 \\ 0, & \alpha \neq k/T_0 \end{cases}$$

 Fig. 2. SCF of BPSK signal when $f = f_c$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1.2R_s)$

 Fig. 4. SCF of QPSK signal when $f = f_c$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1.2R_s)$

 Fig. 3. SOF of BPSK signal when $f = f_c$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1.2R_s)$

 Fig. 5. SOF of QPSK signal when $f = f_c$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1.2R_s)$

where $i \in [s, c]$, $\tilde{R}_c(0) = \tilde{R}_s(0) = 1$.

Similarly, according to the spectral correlation function Eq.(7), if we focus on $f = f_c$ projection of the SCF and SOF, we can derive that for QPSK we have

$$\hat{S}_x^\alpha(f_c)_{(QPSK)} = \frac{T_0}{4} \text{sinc}^2\left(\frac{k}{2}\right), \quad \alpha = k/T_0 \quad (8)$$

and

$$C_x^\alpha(f_c)_{(QPSK)} = 1, \quad \text{when } \alpha = k/T_0, |k| = 1, 3, 5, \dots \quad (9)$$

The SCF and SOF of the QPSK signal are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Similarly, we set the carrier frequency $f_c = 20000$ Hz and the symbol rate of QPSK $R_s = 2500$ Hz.

C. Mixed-signal Detection based on SOF

Based on second-order cyclostationary theory, we have derived the SCF of a mixed signal consisting of multiple independent spectrum components significantly overlapping in the frequency domain in our previous work [10].

Assume the received mixed signal $x(t)$ is composed of two independent signals $x_1(t)$ and $x_2(t)$ with carrier frequencies

f_{c1} and f_{c2} , which are different but very close to each other. Also, we assume that they have different but close symbol rates. The two signals have independent amplitudes, phases and initial time delays, and they transmit through two independent fading channels.

Given the independence of the frequency components in the mixed signal $x(t) = x_1(t) + x_2(t) + n(t)$, the SCF corresponds to:

$$\hat{S}_x^\alpha(f) = \hat{S}_{x_1}^\alpha(f) + \hat{S}_{x_2}^\alpha(f). \quad (10)$$

If we focus on $f = f_c$ projection, we will find that when $\alpha = kR_s(i)$, where $R_s(i) = 1/T_0(i)$ is the symbol rate of i^{th} component, $\hat{S}_x^\alpha(f_c)$ exhibits an impulse which can be exploited to detect the existence of multiple components of each and every component.

After normalization of $S_x^\alpha(f)$ using Eq.(1), we can obtain the SOF $C_x^\alpha(f)$.

At the same time, because SCF and SOF are two variable (f and α) functions, and the carrier frequency of the two components are different, we just focus on the band

$f \in (\hat{f}_c - \hat{B}/2, \hat{f}_c + \hat{B}/2)$ to detect the multiple components.

Next, we use the following three-step algorithm to detect signals and estimate carrier frequencies.

- 1) Step 1: Estimate the mixed signal's carrier frequency \hat{f}_c and null-to-null bandwidth \hat{B} through spectrum analysis.
- 2) Step 2: Calculate the SOF around $\hat{B}/2$ for a cyclic frequency span of \hat{B} with fine resolution.
- 3) Step 3: Identify the number of signals and estimate the symbol rate.

The first step is a simple spectrum analysis and the carrier frequency estimation \hat{f}_c is not very accurate. This estimation is only used for the second step to perform high resolution SOF calculations. Although high resolution SOF calculation is a computationally demanding task, we are not obtaining the entire SOF across the whole cyclic frequency domain. Instead, we are only obtaining SOF at those cyclic frequencies where the SOF features at the symbol rate of each and every individual signal component are expected to exhibit. By doing this, we can significantly reduce the computational complexity.

Fig. 6 shows the SOF of a mixed signal with one BPSK modulated component and one QPSK component with 100% overlap in spectrum. The carrier frequencies are set to $f_{c_1} = 20000$ Hz and $f_{c_2} = 20100$ Hz. The null-to-null bandwidths are set to $B_1 = 5000$ Hz and $B_2 = 4800$ Hz, which means the symbol rates are $R_{s_1} = 2500$ Hz and $R_{s_2} = 2400$ Hz. A raised cosine filter with roll-off factor of 1 is used for both transmitted signals. Fig. 7 shows the spectra of both signals. It is clear from Fig. 7 that the second signal's spectrum is entirely contained within the first signal's spectrum with a 100% overlap. This is the worst case scenario for spectrum overlapping. Here we assume the power of the two components in the received signal are 3 dB different from each other.

Fig. 6. SOF of two different signal components with 100% spectrum overlap

Fig. 8 is the view of Fig. 6 from the α axis. It is evident from Fig. 8 that the two signal components exhibit peaks at k times their symbol rates as predicted by the cyclostationary analysis theory. It is also clear that the SOF peaks are far above the noise floor, hence we can set a universal threshold

Fig. 7. Spectra of two signals with 100% spectrum overlap

Fig. 8. SOF of two different signal components with 100% spectrum overlap (α view)

to determine the number of signal components present in the target. Here, we simply choose a predetermined threshold of 0.2 and count the number of peaks above this threshold, then estimate the symbol rates from the cyclic frequencies of such peaks.

As we can see from Fig. 8, there are 2 peaks at the cyclic frequencies of $\alpha = 2400$ and 2500 Hz, according to Eq.(6) and (9), we can determine that there are 2 components in this mixed signal, and their symbol rates are 2400 and 2500 Hz.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the proposed mixed signal detection and symbol rate estimation algorithm

under various channel conditions, signal to noise ratios, and different signal mixture scenarios.

A. Detection of Different Components with Different Modulation Types

The most significant improvement of this method compared with that proposed in our previous work is that we extend our detection from only BPSK modulation to include both BPSK and QPSK. Fig. 9 shows the SOF of two BPSK signal components and Fig. 10 shows that of two QPSK components. As we can see from the figures, our method can detect different components with different modulation types.

Fig. 9. two BPSK signals with 0 dB received power difference and 100% spectrum overlap

Fig. 10. two QPSK signals with 0 dB received power difference and 100% spectrum overlap

B. Effects of Different Channel Conditions and Noises

The most important factor in mixed-signal detection in this method is the difference in received power between different signal components. In real situations, the transmitted power of signals, the distances between transmitters and receivers, and the fading factor of the channels are quite different. As a direct result, at the receiver side, the received signals' power may be significantly different from others and the weak signal component might be overshadowed by stronger ones. Here, we evaluate the performance under different channel conditions.

Fig. 11 - 12 show the SOF of two signal components with 100% spectrum overlap. Their SNR are set to 10 dB. All the parameters for these experiments are set the same except the relative power of the two components. In Fig. 11, the difference in received power between the two components is 5 dB; and in Fig. 12, the difference is 10 dB. Clearly, we can find that as the received power difference between the two components increases, the detection becomes more difficult. In Fig. 12, the detection algorithm fails to detect the weak signal component.

Fig. 11. two different signals with 5 dB received power difference and 100% spectrum overlap

Now, let us investigate the detection accuracy as a function of the relative power between the mixed signal components. The circle-shaped curve in Fig. 13 demonstrates the detection accuracy versus the received signal power differences. Both signals are transmitted through independent fading channels with a 10 dB received SNR. If the algorithm correctly detects the two signals and accurately estimates their symbol rates, it is counted as a correct detection, otherwise it is deemed incorrect.

As can be seen from the figure, when the received power difference is less than 6 dB, our method has excellent accuracy - higher than 90%. As the difference increases to 10 dB, the detection accuracy gradually falls to around 10%.

Fig. 12. two different BPSK signals with 10 dB received power difference and 100% spectrum overlap

Fig. 13. Received-power differences vs. Detection accuracy for mixed signal detection in Flat fading channel (SNR = 10dB)

The star-shaped curve in Fig. 13 shows the detection/estimation result when the SNR is 0 dB. Compared with the curve of 10 dB, we find the SNR of the channel has little effect on the performance when the received power difference is less than 4 dB. This is the direct result of the noise resistance property of cyclostationary analysis, with noise having no spectrum correlation. In order to increase the detection accuracy, we need to increase the length of the mixed signal, which will increase the complexity of the calculation.

C. Mixed Signal with More Signal Components

The square-shaped curve in Fig. 13 shows detection performance for the case of three modulated signal components in the mixed signal (1 BPSK and 2 QPSK) with every two adjacent components having 100% spectrum overlap and with

a received power difference between the highest and the lowest components of 5 dB. It can be shown that the number of component will have little effect on the detection accuracy.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we employ second-order cyclostationary features to perform signal detection and symbol rate estimation on mixed signals in a spectrally congested and spectrally contested environment. By exploiting the SOF, we can detect the number of signal components and estimate their symbol rate accurately in different channel conditions and signal to noise levels. We also demonstrate the effectiveness and robustness of the proposed method through simulation.

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REFERENCES

- [1] V. Chakravarthy, Z. Wu, M. Temple, and F. Garber, "Novel Overlay/Underlay Cognitive Radio Waveforms Using SD-SMSE Framework to Enhance Spectrum Efficiency - Part I: Theoretical Framework and Analysis in AWGN Channel," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 57, no. 12, pp. 3794-3804, December 2009.
- [2] V. Chakravarthy, Z. Wu and M. Temple, "Novel Overlay/Underlay Cognitive Radio Waveforms Using SD-SMSE Framework to Enhance Spectrum Efficiency - Part II: Analysis in Fading Channel," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 1868-1876, June 2010
- [3] Z. Wu and T. C. Yang, "Blind Cyclostationary Analysis for Underwater Acoustic Communications," *IEEE ICC 2012*
- [4] Z. Wu and T. C. Yang, "Blind Cyclostationary Carrier Frequency and Symbol Rate Estimation for Underwater Acoustic Communications," *IEEE MMTC E-Letter Special Issue on Acoustic and Audio Communication*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 25-29, February 2012
- [5] E. Like, V. Chakravarthy, P. Ratazzi, and Z. Wu, "Signal classification in fading channels using cyclic spectral analysis," *EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, pp. 114, Sep 2009.
- [6] Z. Wu, T. Yang, Z. Liu, and V. Chakravarthy, "Modulation detection of underwater acoustic communication signals through cyclostationary analysis," *IEEE Milcom 2012*, 2012.
- [7] J. Sanderson, X. Li, Z. Liu and Z. Wu, "Hierarchical Blind Modulation Classification for Underwater Acoustic Communication Signal via Cyclostationary and Maximal Likelihood Analysis," *IEEE Milcom 2013*
- [8] R. Zhou, X. Li, T. Yang, Z. Liu and Z. Wu, "Real-time Cyclostationary Analysis for Cognitive Radio via Software Defined Radio," *IEEE Globecom 2012*
- [9] Y. Qu, X. Li and Z. Wu, "Software-Defined Radio based Automatic Blind Hierarchical Modulation Detector via Second-Order Cyclostationary Analysis and Fourth-Order Cumulant," *IEEE Milcom 2013*
- [10] D. Li, Y. Qu, Z. Wu, Z. Liu and Z. Zhang, "Mixed Signal Detection based on Second-order Cyclostationary Features," *IEEE Milcom 2014*
- [11] W. A. Gardner, *Cyclostationarity in Communications and Signal Processing*, IEEE Press, Piscataway, NJ, USA, 1993.
- [12] W. A. Gardner, "The spectral correlation theory of cyclostationary time-series", *Signal Processing*, vol. 11, pp. 13-36, July 1986.
- [13] W. A. Gardner, "Spectral correlation of modulated signals, Part i : Analog modulation," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 1986.
- [14] W. A. Gardner, W. A. Brown, and C.-K. Chen, "Spectral correlation of modulated signals: part ii - digital modulation," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 1987.
- [15] W. A. Gardner, "Signal interception: A unifying theoretical framework for feature detection," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 1988.
- [16] W. A. Gardner, "Statistical Spectral Analysis: A Non-probabilistic Theory," Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall, 1987.